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CROSS-LINGUISTIC SPORTS TERMINOLOGY: TYPOLOGICAL, DESCRIPTIVE, AND COMPONENTIAL ANALYSES OF AZERBAIJANI AND RUSSIAN LEXICAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The goal of this article is to explore the typological features of sports terms in Azerbaijani and Russian, demonstrate their similarities and divergences, and evaluate the degree of influence from international terminological standards, primarily English. It examines definite linguistic sources, semantic classifications, structural types, mechanisms of borrowing, historical influences, and culture-specific elements shaping the terminological systems of both languages. The research contributes to the field of comparative linguistics and terminology studies, emphasizing the growing importance of international sports communication. The typological comparison shows that sports terminology in Azerbaijani and Russian is shaped by international influence, linguistic structure, and cultural history. Despite important differences in morphology and native word formation, both languages demonstrate similar strategies in borrowing and adapting modern sports vocabulary.

Keywords: sports terminology, Azerbaijani language, Russian language, comparative linguistics, typology, componential analysis, lexicography.

Sports terminology is a dynamic lexical subsystem that evolves under the influence of global sporting practices, Olympic movement, mass sports, and the professionalization of athletic disciplines. Linguistic research on sports terminology in Azerbaijani and Russian has gained relevance due to the increasing integration of both languages into international sports communication. It includes examples of comparative, descriptive, and typological linguistic methods. Sports terminology represents a dynamic subsystem of the lexical structure of national languages and reflects both linguistic processes and sociocultural development. The formation of modern sports terminology in the Azerbaijani and Russian languages is shaped by institutional documents, national federations, and international organizations such as the IOC and specialized sports bodies.

In the Azerbaijani context, terminological development has been systematically studied, particularly in relation to the evolution of modern terminology and codification practices¹.

For Russian sports terminology, one of the most authoritative sources remains the explanatory dictionary by Bleer, Suslov, and Tyshler, which provides standardized definitions and semantics of professional sports terms.

The descriptive method was employed to systematically observe and record the features of sports terminology in both languages. For example, in analyzing the Azerbaijani term *güləşçi* (wrestler), the method involved breaking down the word into its root *güləş* and agentive suffix *-çi* to describe its morphological structure and semantic function. Similarly, the Russian term *борец* was analyzed as root *бор-* plus suffix *-ец*. The descriptive method allows precise identification of morphemes, word formation patterns, and meaning relationships.

The comparative-typological method was applied to identify parallels and differences in sports terminology between Azerbaijani and Russian. Examples include:

Concept	Azerbaijani Term	Russian Term	Observations
Wrestler	<i>güləşçi</i>	<i>борец</i>	Both use derivational suffixes to form agent nouns; Azerbaijani uses agglutinative <i>-çi</i> , Russian fusional <i>-ец</i>
Runner	<i>qaçışçı</i>	<i>бегун</i>	Parallel agentive constructions; morphological structures differ due to language type
Freestyle wrestling	<i>sərbəst güləş</i>	<i>вольная борьба</i>	Both are compound terms; Azerbaijani nominal cluster, Russian adjective+noun
Speed training	<i>sürət məşqi</i>	<i>скоростная тренировка</i>	Multiword technical term; attribute position differs (post-nominal in AZ, pre-nominal in RU)
Ball Control	<i>topa nəzarət</i>	<i>контроль мяча</i>	Phrase structure illustrates syntactic variation while maintaining semantic equivalence

¹ Həsənov, R. *Azərbaycan dilində terminologiyanın inkişafı*, Bakı, 2020

The **componential analysis** method was used to break down complex sports terms into their semantic features (components) to reveal shared and distinctive

elements. The same examples can be presented using the comparative analysis method.

Term	Semantic Components	Language
<i>güləşçi</i> (wrestler)	[+human], [+athlete], [+wrestler]	Azerbaijani
<i>борец</i> (wrestler)	[+human], [+athlete], [+wrestler]	Russian
<i>sürət məşqi</i> (speed training)	[+training], [+speed], [+physical]	Azerbaijani
<i>скоростная тренировка</i> (speed training)	[+training], [+speed], [+physical]	Russian
<i>hücumçu</i> (forward)	[+human], [+athlete], [+offense], [+team role]	Azerbaijani
<i>нападающий</i> (forward)	[+human], [+athlete], [+offense], [+team role]	Russian

This method highlights the core semantic features, showing how similar roles and actions are represented across both languages while allowing for nuanced differences in lexical expression.

The typological comparison shows that sports terminology in Azerbaijani and Russian is shaped by international influence, linguistic structure, and cultural history. Despite important differences in morphology and native word formation, both languages demonstrate similar strategies in borrowing and adapting modern sports vocabulary.

Typological analysis also involves comparing dictionaries across languages based on their structure, content, purpose, and lexicographic principles. In the context of sports terminology, Russian and Azerbaijani lexicography show both shared traditions and language-specific characteristics. The typological comparison shows that Russian sports lexicography is more developed in terms of standardization, dictionary volume, and explanatory depth. Azerbaijani sports dictionaries, influenced by Russian and global English terminology, are still growing and tend to be translation-oriented. Both languages share many international sports terms, but structural, morphological, and semantic representation differs substantially.

Talking about general lexicographic background, we can say that Azerbaijani sports terminology has developed mainly during the 20th–21st centuries alongside modernization of national sports and international integration (AFFA, PFL, National Olympic Committee documents). Many terms originated from Russian and English, especially during the Soviet period and after independence. Dictionaries tend to be translation-oriented, focusing on practical use.

Russian sports lexicography is older and more extensive, with dictionaries from Soviet times and modern corpora. Terminology is relatively standardized due to strong sports federations and scientific literature. Russian dictionaries are often explanatory and encyclopedic.

Typological Features that are common for both Languages are

Both languages exhibit substantial influence from English-based global terminology.

Azerbaijani maintains clearer morphological transparency due to its agglutinative nature.

Russian supports deeper historical layers from French, German, and Slavic sources.

Here are some examples from Russian Sports Terminological Dictionaries / Corpora

1. From *Терминология спорта: толковый словарь-справочник* by A. N. Bleer, F. P. Suslov, D. A. Tyshler²

e.g. Снаряды спортивные — “a number of special industrial items intended for the performance of particular exercises and having characteristics regulated by competition rules; for example: athletics (discus, shot put, pole), weightlifting (barbell, kettlebells, dumbbells)”.

e.g. Спартакиада — “a complex multi-sport competition that includes several sports, historically held in the Soviet Union, such as Spartakiads of republics, workers, schools, etc.”

e.g. Гандикап — although not originally Russian, used in Russian sports lexicon to mean the “system allowing weaker participants to have an advantage, e.g., in multi-stage competitions.”

2. From linguistic / corpus-based analysis (ice hockey terminology)

In the paper *Structural and semantic features of sports terms (on the example of ice hockey)*, authors analyze terms like «шайба» (“puck”) and «клюшка» (“stick”).

Шайба: its meaning in ice hockey goes beyond just “puck” — in contexts, semantic components include [+object], [+flat], [+used in gameplay], and metaphorical or metonymic meanings (because in match commentary, size, shape, weight are often evoked).

Клюшка: similarly, it denotes “hockey stick” but the analysis shows its multi-layered semantics in corpora, especially descriptive speech of commentators.

3. From linguistic research on borrowings in Russian sports terminology

In the article *Borrowings in Russian Sports Terminology* (Musina G., Satarova L) the authors use the “Dictionary of Sports Terms” by R. R. Salimzyanov as a key source.³

They list two-component and three-component borrowed or compound sports terms, for example:

² Bleer, A. N., Suslov, F. P., Tyshler, D. A. *Terminologiya sporta: tolkovyy slovar-spravochnik*. (Sports Terminology: An Explanatory Dictionary and Reference Guide) Moscow, 2010.

³ Borrowings in Russian sports terminology Musina G. F. Satarova L, 2023

полуфинал (semifinal), *хет-трик* (hat-trick), *интенсивность тренировки* (training intensity), *теория физической культуры* (theory of physical culture).

Here are some comparing examples from Official Documents (AFFA, PFL, and other Azerbaijani Sports Federations)

1. AFFA (Association of the Football Federations of Azerbaijan) – Registration / Player Passport (“BURAXILIŞ 2025”)⁴

In the AFFA document *BURAXILIŞ 2025: Qeydiyyat qaydaları və futbolçu pasportunun tərtibi* (Release 2025 – Registration & Player Passport Rules), the term “*futbolçu pasportu*” (“player passport”) is used.

Typological note: This is a compound term in Azerbaijani: *futbolçu and pasportu* (“player and his/its passport”).

Terminological significance: It refers to a formal identity document specifically for footballers, not a general personal passport — showing institutional terminology in registration systems.

2. AFFA – Licensing for Coaches / Clubs

In the issue of 2025, there is mention of “*müvafiq məşqçilik lisenziyası*” (“relevant coaching license”).

Typological note: This is a phrase (multiword term) — *məşqçilik* (“coaching”) + *lisenziyası* (“license”).

Terminological significance: This is a key regulatory term used in the federation’s licensing system, and indicates how “license / lisenziya” is borrowed but adapted into Azerbaijani governance language.

3. AFFA – Age-Group League Regulatory Term

In the AFFA U-11 League Statutes (“*Əsasnamə*”) document, the terms “*iştirakçı komanda*”, “*liqa*”, and “*Fair-Play prinsipləri*” appear.

“*Iştirakçı komanda*” = “participating team” — a technical phrase in the rules.

“*Liqa*” = “league” — used in Azerbaijani though borrowed from foreign sports vocabulary.

“*Fair-Play prinsipləri*” = “fair play principles” — a direct borrowing of the English “fair play”.⁵

4. AFFA – U-14 Girls League Statutes

In the AFFA U-14 Girls League Regulations (*Əsasnamə*), the phrase “*komanda forması*” (team uniform), “*texniki zona*” (technical zone), and “*yüksək rəqəm*” (“number on the back”) are used.

Typological note: These are multiword regulatory terms.

Terminological significance: They reflect the formal language used by national federation to regulate match, uniforms, and match protocol.

5. Azərbaycan Tennis Federasiyası (Azerbaijan Tennis Federation)

In the “*Tennis idman növü üzrə idmançılara lisenziyaların verilməsi qaydası*” (Azerbaijan Tennis Federation’s Rules on Granting Licenses to Athletes), the

document defines “*konversiya prosesi*”, “*sezon*”, “*idman klubu*”, and “*sağlamlıq kağızı*”.

“*Konversiya prosesi*” (“conversion process”) — the change of license type, institutional term.

“*Sezon*” (“season”) — borrowed but institutionalized.⁶

“*Idman klubu*” (“sport club”) — standard institution term.

“*Sağlamlıq kağızı*” (“health certificate / document”) — formal term used in licensing.

Here are examples from Russian Federations / National Olympic Committee documents

1. Use of “Олимпийский” in Official Names (ROC)

According to the Russian Olympic Committee’s document “*Об использовании слова ‘олимпийский’*” (“On the use of the word ‘Olympic’”) the ROC regulates how organizations can use “олимпийский - olympic”, “паралимпийский- paralympic”, and “сурдлимпийский- deaflympic” in their titles.⁷

Here we can say that according to the Terminological notes:

“Олимпийский комитет России” (“Olympic Committee of Russia”) – institutional name, shows a formalized term, “слово «олимпийский – word Olympic» ... или образованные на его основе словосочетания – and based on it a word combination” – demonstrates a terminological rule about word formation (root + derived phrases).

This is a governance term, not a sports technique, but very important for the terminological system because it defines how “Olympic / Paralympic” are used in organizational contexts.

2. Resolution of the Ministry of Sport on Use of “Олимпийский” / “Паралимпийский” / “Сурдлимпийский”

Приказ Министра спорта РФ № 912 от 11.12.2020 (the Resolution of the Ministry of Sport of Russian Federation No 912 from 11.12.2020) establishes the **procedure for sports organizations** (which run educational sports programs) to use in their name: “олимпийский- Olympic”, “паралимпийский- paralympic” or “сурдлимпийский- deaflympic” or derivatives thereof.

Terminological significance: This legal / regulatory document standardizes the use of these highly loaded institutional terms — it is a terminological regulation rather than purely technical sport vocabulary.

3. Federal Law on Sport (329-ФЗ)

In **Federal Law No. 329-ФЗ “On Physical Culture and Sport”**, there is a clear terminological definition of “*спорт / спортивная деятельность – sport/sports activities*”, “*вид спорта- kind of sport*”, and also for “*паралимпийское движение – Paralympic movement / специальная олимпиада России- special Olympic of Russia / Сурдлимпийский комитет – deaflympic committee*”, etc.

Examples from the law:

⁴ 3. AFFA (Association of Football Federations of Azerbaijan). *Qeydiyyat qaydaları və futbolçu pasportu*.

⁵ 4. AFFA. *U-11 Liqa Əsasnaməsi*. Official publications

⁶ Azerbaijan Tennis Federation. *Tennis idman növü üzrə idmançılara lisenziyaların verilməsi qaydası*.

⁷ Russian Olympic Committee. *Ob ispol'zovanii slova «olimpiyskiy»*. olympic.ru.

«вид спорта – kind of sport» — a legally defined concept (“sport type / discipline”) in the context of national registration and regulatory classification.

“паралимпийское движение России – Paralympic movement of Russia”, “сурдлимпийское движение России– deaflympic movement of Russia” — formal institutional terminology embedded in legal state-level sport definitions.

4. Documents of the Sports Federation — Russian Federation of Alpine Skiing (RFGS)

On the RFGS (Российская федерация горнолыжного спорта–Russian Alpine Skiing Federation) website under “Документы - documents”, they publish *Правила вида спорта – Rules of the kind of sport “горнолыжный спорт”* (alpine skiing) approved by the Ministry of Sport.

Terminological examples:

“вид спорта” — “type of sport” (this term is both legal and technical in the rules).

“Квалификационные критерии” (“Qualification criteria”) may appear in these rules, referring to athlete eligibility, ranking, competition structure.⁸

5. Regulations of Equestrian Sport (FEI, via Russian Federation)

In the *Общий регламент, 24-е издание* (General Regulations, 24th edition) on the Russian equestrian

federation site, it states that athletes, teams, or staff must be “заявлены своим Национальным Олимпийским Комитетом” (“declared by their National Olympic Committee”).⁹

Terminological points:

Use of “Национальный Олимпийский Комитет” (“National Olympic Committee”) — formal institutional term.

“Официальное лицо команды” (“an official team person”) — technical-regulatory phrase.

“критерии допуска” (“admission / qualification criteria”) — rule-based term used in the regulatory system.

Globalization accelerates term borrowing and linguistic convergence. Similarities could be revealed in

- Alphabetical dictionaries (e.g., *Idman terminlärinin lügəti- Dictionary of Sports Terms, Словарь спортивных терминов*).

- Thematic/discipline-based dictionaries (football, athletics, wrestling).

- Multilingual dictionaries (AZ–RU–EN; RU–EN–DE, etc.).

Typological differences between Russian and Azerbaijani sports dictionaries are the following:

Features of structural differences	Azerbaijani sports dictionaries	Russian sports dictionaries
Type	Mostly bilingual (AZ–RU, AZ–EN)	Often monolingual (RU) or multilingual
Definiton Style	Short, practical, translation-focused	Detailed, scientific, sometimes encyclopedic
Examples	Not always provided	Frequently included
Borrowed terms often assimilate phonologically and morphologically (<i>пенальти, дриблинг</i>).	Lower variability of terms	Higher standardized terms through federations

Semantically Russian dictionaries tend to include:

- broader semantic explanations,
- phraseology (e.g., *вне игры, домашний матч, игра в один касание*),

and Azerbaijani dictionaries:

- focus on equivalents rather than semantic nuances,

• phraseology is less represented,

• fewer stylistic notes.

Observing typological patterns taken from dictionaries it can be said that Azerbaijani Dictionaries are mostly translation-based and concise. They provide only essential functional definitions. There are often lack classification, variants, examples, or stylistic labels in the dictionaries. Less standardized terminology across sources can be revealed.

Russian Dictionaries are detailed, explanatory, often encyclopedic. They provide rule-based, scientific,

or technical classifications, include stylistic labels, examples, subentries. Dictionaries are highly standardized due to federation and Soviet lexicographic tradition.

References

1. Həsənov, R. *Azərbaycan dilində terminologiyanın inkişafı*. Bakı., 2020

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3. Borrowings in Russian sports terminology Musina G. F. Satarova L, 2023

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⁸ RFGS (Russian Federation of Alpine Skiing). *Pravila vida sporta «gornolyzhnyy sport»*

⁹ FEI (International Federation for Equestrian Sports). *General Regulations*.

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